

POTENTIALS, RISKS, AND ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS IN THE UTILIZATION OF AI-POWERED TOOLS IN EDUCATION PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the perspectives of educators on the use of AI-powered tools in education, analyze the ethical implications, and propose a framework for responsible utilization. The study was conducted in 10 schools in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, known for their urban location and reliable internet accessibility. A validated interview questionnaire was utilized to gather viewpoints on AI-powered tools, benefits, risks, and ethical considerations. The findings highlighted significant utilization of AI-powered tools in education, including virtual tutoring systems, virtual assistants, chatbots, content creation and recommendation systems, video conferencing applications, and assessment tools. Perceived benefits included enhanced content creation, virtual tutoring support, improved accessibility to information, and administrative efficiency, while perceived risks included overdependence on AI, academic integrity problems, automation concerns, biases, privacy, accuracy and reliability issues. The use of AI-powered tools in education raises ethical concerns, particularly regarding academic integrity. Participants expressed apprehensions about plagiarism and copyright infringement, emphasizing the risk of students exploiting AI to copy content without proper citation, potentially undermining the reliability of academic output. Furthermore, concerns are raised about academic dishonesty, including using AI for exam answers and using AI-generated content as original work, prompting a need for comprehensive strategies to balance the benefits of AI integration with ethical considerations to preserve academic integrity. Overall, the study underscores the importance of responsible AI utilization to maximize benefits while minimizing risks, advocating for clear ethical guidelines, critical thinking skills development, further research, and policy framework for ethical utilization of AI-powered tools in education.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence Tools, Potentials, Risks, Ethical Implications, Policy Framework*

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century has been marked by unprecedented technological advancements that have profoundly influenced nearly every facet of human existence. Among the most notable of these influences is the transformation observed in the field of education, largely driven by the proliferation of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. The integration of AI into educational settings has introduced a range of tools that offer significant potential to enhance both teaching and learning. AI-powered educational tools, including intelligent tutoring systems and adaptive learning platforms, are designed to cater to individual students' needs, learning paces, and styles, thereby fostering greater engagement and comprehension (De La Vall & Araya, 2023). Moreover, the automation of administrative tasks by AI tools enables educators to devote more time to high-value activities such as personalized student interactions.

Recent studies highlight the extensive adoption of AI-based tools in educational contexts. For instance, Garrel and Mayer (2023) found that 63.4% of German students utilize AI tools like ChatGPT for their studies. These statistics underscore the widespread acceptance and application of AI tools in education.

However, the rapid integration of these technologies into educational practices raises several ethical concerns. Issues related to biases, data privacy (Selwyn, 2019), technological dependency (Ghosh et al., 2019), and educator autonomy (Deci & Ryan, 2020) are increasingly prominent. The potential for AI tools to mimic human writing poses additional challenges, such as the risk of academic dishonesty. Despite 75% of students acknowledging the unethical nature of cheating using AI apps, over 30% believe their teachers lack awareness of this issue (Intelligent.com, 2023). These challenges highlight the urgent need for ethical oversight and the development of responsible policies governing the use of AI in education.

The purpose of this study is to investigate educators' perspectives on the use of AI tools in educational settings, focusing on their experiences, challenges, and ethical concerns. By analyzing these perspectives, the study aims to contribute to the formulation of policies and guidelines that address potential harms while maximizing the benefits of AI in education. The findings are expected to provide a foundation for administrators to develop ethical principles and best practices, ensuring that AI tools are used responsibly and effectively to support students' educational needs.

Understanding educators' perspectives on the utilization of AI is crucial for crafting policies that mitigate potential harms while maximizing benefits. A comprehensive analysis of these perspectives will facilitate the formulation of ethical principles and best practices that address educators' concerns and ensure that AI-powered tools effectively support students' educational needs. This study aims to establish a foundational

framework for administrators to develop policies and guidelines regarding the ethical use of AI within educational settings.

The integration of AI into education promises substantial improvements in both teaching and learning outcomes. AI-driven tools have the potential to revolutionize educational experiences by personalizing lessons, automating administrative tasks, and enhancing accessibility. Nonetheless, the advancement of AI also presents significant ethical and societal challenges. To foster an inclusive and equitable learning environment, it is imperative to establish clear policies and guidelines that govern the responsible use of AI in education.

Theoretical frameworks such as the Computational Theory of Mind (McCulloch & Pitts, 1943) provide insights into the similarities between human cognition and computational processes, influencing the development of AI algorithms. The concept of Technological Singularity (von Neumann, 1958) raises concerns about the implications of machines surpassing human intelligence, emphasizing the need for ethical considerations to guide AI's growth (Williams, 2021). Additionally, the study of Machine Ethics or Morality explores the ethical dimensions of AI systems and their decision-making capabilities. The Capability Approach (Nussbaum, 2007) offers a framework for evaluating AI's role in enhancing human agency and autonomy.

The incorporation of AI in education, exemplified by intelligent tutoring systems and adaptive learning platforms, represents a significant advancement. These tools can provide personalized instruction and automate grading processes, improving efficiency and effectiveness (Anderson et al., 1995; Ritter et al., 2007). AI's impact extends to language learning and educational management systems, offering tailored support and enhancing accessibility (Abdulla, 2023; Blikstein, 2018). Despite these benefits, ethical concerns, including data privacy and the potential for increased inequality, must be addressed (Selwyn, 2019).

In summary, the integration of AI in education necessitates a balanced approach that considers both the transformative potential and the ethical implications. Establishing robust guidelines and regulatory frameworks will ensure that AI technologies are used responsibly, promoting equitable access and safeguarding educational integrity.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the varying perspectives of educators on the utilization of AI-powered tools within the secondary schools of Tagbilaran City, for school year 2023-2024, analyze the ethical implications of their use, and contribute to the development of a policy framework for responsible and equitable implementation.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What AI-powered tools are commonly used by educators in the secondary schools of Tagbilaran City?
2. What are the potential benefits of AI-powered tools in education?

3. What are the perceived risks associated with AI-powered tools in education?
4. What are the ethical implications in the utilization of AI-powered tools in education?
5. What policy framework can be developed to address the issues on the utilization of AI-powered tools in education?

METHODOLOGY

This succeeding discussion deals with the research design, subjects of this investigation, research environment, data gathering procedure, the instrument used, and the statistical technique employed in testing the data.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative design to thoroughly explore the collective perspectives and experiences of educators, specifically school heads and teachers, regarding the utilization of AI-powered tools in educational institutions. Purposive sampling was used to select participants, focusing on school heads and teachers who were familiar with and actively employed AI tools in their administrative functions and pedagogical practices. Individual interviews were conducted to gather insights into their experiences and opinions concerning artificial intelligence. Through this approach, the researcher aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the viewpoints and ethical implications associated with AI-powered tools in education, which would contribute to the development of policy frameworks, strategies, and ethical guidelines for the responsible application of AI tools.

Research Environment

The research was conducted across ten schools in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, including four private and six public schools. The selection of these institutions was based on their geographic location, which was primarily urban and provided easy access to the Internet. Internet connectivity was considered crucial for this study due to its reliance on AI tools requiring online access. Additionally, the researcher's established connections with the secondary schools were essential in facilitating the study.

Research Participants

The study involved school heads and teachers from ten secondary schools in Tagbilaran City, Bohol, including six public and four private institutions. A total of 4 school heads and 11 teachers participated, offering insights into the use of AI-powered tools in education. The participation was predominantly from teachers due to the limited familiarity of school heads with AI tools.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents

School	Type of School		Number of Participants	
	Public	Private	School Heads	Teachers
A	✓		1	1
B	✓			1
C	✓		1	1
D	✓			1
E	✓		1	
F	✓			1
G		✓		1
H		✓		1
I		✓	1	2
J		✓		2
Total	6	4	4	11

Research Instrument

This study utilized a validated, self-designed interview questionnaire. The tool was reviewed and validated by experts in ICT and education to examine various viewpoints and ethical considerations regarding using AI-powered tools in educational settings. The questionnaire targeted teachers and school heads to gather insights on how AI tools affected their responsibilities, potential benefits and risks, and ethical issues. The findings were intended to inform the development of policies and recommendations for AI's effective and ethical use in education.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection began with obtaining permission from the Program Head of the Graduate Studies. Following this, the researcher sought approval from the Tagbilaran City Schools Division Superintendent. Formal requests were then sent to the heads of public and private schools. Once approvals were granted, a pre-survey was conducted to identify eligible teachers and school heads who met the criteria. Selected participants received a consent form outlining the study's purpose and procedures. After obtaining their consent, interview schedules were arranged with the participants to ensure convenience and adherence to ethical standards. The interview venues were chosen by the respondents, considering accessibility and availability.

Data Analysis

The data collected from the interviews were processed through the following steps: First, the audio recordings were transcribed verbatim. Next, the transcribed data were systematically organized and coded for analysis. Patterns, themes, and relationships within the data were then identified. Thematic analysis was employed to uncover recurring themes, patterns, and detailed descriptions in the qualitative data. This approach

facilitated the comparison and validation of results. Finally, the identified themes were interpreted within the context of the research objectives and relevant literature.

By synthesizing the findings, the study provided valuable insights for policymakers, curriculum planners, and educators regarding AI's transformative potential and ethical challenges. It assisted in the development of policies that ensure the ethical use of AI in education.

RESULTS

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the study's findings. Employing thematic analysis, the researcher examines school heads' and teachers' perspectives on using AI-powered tools in educational settings, analyzes the ethical implications, and contributes to developing a framework for responsible and equitable integration of these tools.

Table 2 reflects the participants' responses regarding the AI-powered educational tools they have used.

Table 2. Respondents' commonly used AI-powered tools in education

Category	Code
1. Intelligent Tutoring System	Photomath, Brainly, Duolingo, Perplexity
2. Virtual Assistant and Chatbots/Content Creation and Recommendation System	Grammarly, Co-pilot, Quillbot, Chat GPT Gemini, Elicit.org, Slides AI, Canva AI
3. Video Conferencing and Messaging Apps	Zoom, Google Meet, Messenger
4. Assessment Grading Tool	Gradedcam, Zipgrade

The research respondents identified several categories of AI-powered tools they have used, as detailed in Table 2. These categories were based on the tools' functions or modes of operation.

Category 1: Intelligent Tutoring Systems include tools like Photomath, Brainly, Duolingo, and Perplexity. These systems provide personalized and adaptive learning experiences, supporting school heads, teachers, and students by addressing their specific needs.

Category 2: Virtual Assistants, Chatbots, and Content Creation Tools encompass examples such as Grammarly, Co-pilot, Quillbot, ChatGPT, Gemini, Elicit.org, Slides AI, and Canva AI. These tools assist educators with creating content, writing tasks, and multimedia production, enhancing instructional techniques and lesson planning.

Category 3: Video Conferencing and Messaging Applications, including Zoom, Google Meet, and Messenger, play a significant role in remote learning by facilitating collaboration and communication in hybrid or distance learning environments.

Category 4: Assessment Grading Tools, such as Zip Grade and Gradecam, automate the grading process, offering efficient and accurate feedback. These tools help optimize instructional time and provide prompt feedback to students.

The utilization of these AI-powered tools has a notable impact on educational methodologies, offering various approaches to meeting learning needs, improving teaching efficacy, and adapting to dynamic educational settings.

Table 3. Perceived benefits of AI-powered tools in education

Category	Code
1. Enhanced Content Creation or Content Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Error reduction and enhanced output quality • Tailored lessons • Innovative strategies • Idea generation enrichment
2. Virtual Tutoring and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved learning outcomes • Promotion of active learning • Facilitated learning • Reinforcement of understanding
3. Virtual Assistant and Chatbots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader range of ideas • Valuable resource assistance • Enhancement of teaching styles and instructional practices
4. Enhanced Accessibility to Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous availability and rapid response provision • Increased speed and convenient access to valuable information
5. Administrative Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased productivity • Reduced workload and stress • Time efficiency • Automated quiz grading and calculation

Table 3 outlines the respondents' views on the benefits of using AI-powered tools in education. The advantages, categorized into several groups, include enhanced content creation, virtual tutoring and support, virtual assistants and chatbots, and improved accessibility to information and administrative efficiency.

Category 1: Enhanced Content Creation or Innovation highlights how AI tools aid in developing new educational content, reducing errors, and improving the quality of outputs. Respondents reported that AI tools facilitate lesson planning tailored to students' preferences and abilities, introduce innovative teaching methods, and generate additional ideas. These benefits are particularly valuable for lesson planning and addressing instructional needs.

Category 2: Virtual Assistants, Chatbots, and Tutoring reflects the significant advantages of AI tools that support teachers and students. Virtual assistants and chatbots provide diverse ideas, promote active learning, and reinforce concepts. This aligns with research by Idroes et al., which noted that AI's role as a virtual assistant enhances lesson delivery and real-time support, benefiting the teaching process (Idroes et al., 2023).

Category 3: Enhanced Accessibility to Information demonstrates how AI tools improve the speed and convenience of information retrieval. Respondents noted that AI facilitates continuous access to valuable resources, thereby increasing productivity and efficiency. This finding supports Di Xu and Jaggars' (2014) assertion that AI-driven tools offer continuous support and guidance, enhancing the learning environment. Idroes et al. (2023) also highlighted AI's role in providing universal access to education, including for students with special needs.

Category 4: Administrative Efficiency illustrates AI's impact on streamlining administrative tasks, such as grading and quiz calculations. Respondents reported that AI tools reduce workload and stress by automating these tasks, which aligns with Ritters' findings that AI enhances grading efficiency and feedback quality (Ritter et al., 2007). This automation allows educators to focus on other essential aspects of teaching, improving overall productivity and creating a more engaging learning environment.

The utilization of AI-powered tools offers significant benefits in enhancing educational methodologies, improving content creation, supporting teaching and learning processes, and optimizing administrative tasks.

Table 4. Perceived risks or drawbacks caused by AI-powered tools

Category	Code
1. Overdependence on AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependency on AI-generated ideas or concepts, • Reduced critical thinking, creativity, and academic engagement • Student laziness
2. Academic Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in authenticating students' outputs • Plagiarism/Copyright infringement • Inadequacy of the element of originality in students' outputs
3. Displacement of Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher job displacement • Teacher workforce reduction • Instructional dilution
4. Biases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perspective limitation caused by biased algorithms • Misinformation proliferation
5. Privacy Concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data privacy violation • Security risks • Unauthorized data access
6. Accuracy and Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deprivation of authentic learning • Erroneous quality of content • Unreliability of output
7. Cost and Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational resource inequities

Table 4 presents the perceived risks and drawbacks associated with AI-powered tools as identified by the respondents. The key areas of concern include overdependence on AI, academic integrity, teacher displacement, biases, privacy concerns, accuracy and reliability, and cost and access.

Category 1: Overdependence on AI highlights the risk that excessive reliance on AI may undermine critical thinking, creativity, and academic engagement among students. Respondents expressed concern that this could foster a culture of student laziness. This aligns with Walter's (2024) findings, which suggest that AI might diminish critical thinking skills.

Category 2: Academic Integrity addresses concerns about verifying the authenticity of students' work. Respondents worried that AI tools could lead to plagiarism and copyright infringement, compromising the originality and uniqueness of student outputs.

Category 3: Teacher Displacement reflects fears that AI might lead to job loss and a decrease in instructional quality due to automation of teaching tasks. Automation could reduce the demand for human labor in tasks like grading and administrative duties, potentially displacing teachers and affecting the quality of education. This concern highlights the potential loss of personalized attention and the unique skills educators bring to the learning process.

Category 4: Bias involves the limitations arising from biased algorithms, including the spread of misinformation. These issues could exacerbate social injustices and undermine efforts for inclusive education. Biased algorithms may lead to inaccurate educational content, impeding students' ability to evaluate information critically.

Category 5: Privacy Concerns pertain to potential data privacy breaches, security vulnerabilities, and unauthorized data access. The increased use of technology in education raises risks of data breaches, threatening the confidentiality of sensitive information and potentially diminishing trust in educational platforms. Effective data protection mechanisms and clear privacy policies are crucial to addressing these issues.

Category 6: Accuracy and Reliability concerns the quality and dependability of AI-generated content. Respondents noted occasional flaws or inaccuracies in AI outputs, emphasizing the need for rigorous review processes to ensure the accuracy and reliability of AI-produced information.

Category 7: Cost and Access highlights the risk of increasing inequities in educational resources due to the unequal availability of AI technologies. High costs and limited internet connectivity can widen the digital divide, as noted by Taylor (2023). This concern aligns with the 2021 European Commission Report and UNESCO's advocacy for strategic goals and fair utilization of AI in education, stressing the importance of addressing disparities in AI access and infrastructure (Nguyen et al., 2022; UNESCO).

Addressing these concerns is crucial for ensuring AI's responsible and equitable integration in education.

Table 5. Ethical implications in the utilization of AI-powered tools in education

Category	Code
Academic Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• plagiarism• copyright infringement• dishonest behavior to gain an unfair advantage in academic assessments/cheating• collaborating with others using AI without permission• difficulty in authenticating students' outputs• inadequacy of the element of originality in students' outputs

Table 5 outlines the ethical implications of integrating AI-powered tools in education. The primary ethical concern identified is academic integrity. Respondents highlighted several issues related to this domain:

Firstly, there is a significant concern about plagiarism and copyright infringement. Respondents noted that students might be tempted to copy content directly from AI-generated sources without proper citation, thereby compromising academic integrity and originality. Such behavior violates established ethical norms and undermines the credibility of students' work.

Additionally, participants expressed worries about academic dishonesty, including the potential for students to use AI technology to generate answers for examinations or produce academic work that is presented as their own without acknowledging the original sources. This misuse of AI tools could provide an unfair advantage and distort the assessment of student performance.

Educators also face challenges in verifying the authenticity of student outputs, especially when AI tools heavily assist in content creation. This situation complicates evaluating the originality of student work and raises concerns about the genuineness of responses.

These concerns collectively underscore the ethical implications of AI in education, emphasizing the need to address these issues to uphold academic integrity. To effectively manage these implications, adopting a balanced approach that integrates AI technology while implementing strategies to mitigate its potential drawbacks is crucial. This approach is essential for preserving the integrity of student learning and maintaining educational priorities in the digital age.

Table 6. Summary of themes on the potentials, risks, and ethical implications in the utilization of AI-powered tools in education

AI-powered Tools Commonly Used by Respondents	Perceived Benefits of AI-powered Tools Used in Education	Perceived Risks of AI-powered Tools Used in Education	Ethical Implications of AI-powered Tools
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intelligent Tutoring System • Creation and Recommendation System • Virtual Assistant and Chatbots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced Content Creation or Content Innovation • Virtual Tutoring and Support • Virtual Assistant and Chatbots • Enhanced Accessibility to Information • Administrative Efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overdependence on AI • Displacement of Teachers • Bias • Privacy Concerns • Accuracy and Reliability • Cost and Access 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic Integrity

Table 6 summarizes the themes related to four specific sub-problems concerning using AI-powered tools in education. The first column lists the AI-driven tools utilized by respondents. The second column details the benefits perceived from these tools. The third column outlines the perceived risks or drawbacks identified by participants. The final column, "Ethical Implications of AI-Powered Tools," highlights the complex ethical issues associated with AI in education. This table provides a comprehensive overview of the benefits, risks, and ethical considerations, offering valuable insights into the challenges and advantages of AI integration in educational settings.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The following are the significant findings of the study:

1. AI-Powered Tools Commonly Used in Education

The findings revealed that the respondents utilized a diverse range of AI-powered tools in education across various categories. Within the context of Intelligent Tutoring Systems, the respondents commonly employed Photomath, Brainly, Duolingo, and Perplexity to enhance teaching and learning experiences.

Similarly, Virtual Assistants, Chatbots, and Content Creation and Recommendation Systems have been predominantly utilized. Tools such as Grammarly, Co-pilot, Quillbot, Chat GPT, Gemeni, Elicit.org, Slides AI, and Canva AI are particularly popular among users.

Additionally, Video Conferencing and messaging applications like Zoom, Google Meet, and Messenger are extensively utilized for remote learning and collaboration.

Finally, assessment and grading tools such as Gradercam and Zipgrade are employed for efficient evaluation processes. Overall, these findings indicate the

significant integration of AI-powered tools in education, catering to various needs from tutoring and content creation to assessment and communication.

2. Perceived Benefits of Using AI-powered Tools in Education

The perceived benefits of using AI-powered tools cut across various categories. In terms of enhanced content creation or innovation, the respondents highlighted benefits such as error reduction, improved output quality, tailored lessons, innovative strategies, and enrichment in idea generation. Virtual Tutoring and Support through AI tools were perceived to improve learning outcomes, promote active learning, facilitate learning processes, and reinforce comprehension. Virtual Assistants and Chatbots were seen as broadening the range of ideas, providing valuable resource assistance, and enhancing teaching styles and instructional practices. Enhanced accessibility to information was observed, including continuous availability and prompt response provision, increased speed, and convenient access to valuable information.

Administrative efficiency benefits included increased productivity, reduced workload and stress for teachers, time efficiency, and automated quiz grading and calculation, signifying the multifaceted advantages perceived by users or respondents.

3. Perceived Risks or Drawbacks of Using AI-powered Tools

The findings regarding the risks of using AI-powered tools, as per respondents' perspectives, highlight several aspects:

Overdependence on AI was identified as a risk factor, leading to dependency on AI-generated ideas, reduced critical thinking, creativity, and academic engagement resulting to student laziness. Academic integrity problems were also raised, including difficulty in verifying authenticity of students' outputs, plagiarism and copyright infringement issues.

The automation stemming from the use of AI-powered tools also raised concerns about teacher displacement, workforce reduction, and instructional dilution. Biases were also identified as well, such as perspective limitations caused by biased algorithms and the proliferation of misinformation. Additionally, privacy concerns, such as data privacy violations, security risks, and unauthorized data access, were identified. Furthermore, accuracy and reliability issues were pointed out, like the deprivation of authentic learning experiences, erroneous content quality, and the unreliability of outputs. Cost and access inequalities were also recognized, indicating inequities in educational resource distribution. These findings showed the multifaceted risks associated with the adoption of AI-powered tools in education, necessitating careful consideration and mitigation strategies.

4. Ethical Implications on the Utilization of AI-Powered tools in education

The incorporation of artificial intelligence (AI) into the field of education has given rise to a number of ethical concerns, with a particular focus on the issue of academic integrity. The respondent's express concerns regarding the potential for AI to facilitate plagiarism and academic dishonesty, thereby compromising the principles of originality

and authenticity in academic work. Educators also encounter significant challenges when it comes to verifying student outputs that heavily rely on artificial intelligence. Addressing these concerns is essential to uphold academic integrity, necessitating a balanced approach that maximizes AI's benefits while reducing potential drawbacks to prioritize student learning and development in the digital era.

Conclusions

Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds immense promise in improving various aspects of life, particularly in education where it offers a multitude of benefits. mOREver, alongside these advantages, it is important to address the potential negative impacts it brings. Focus should be placed on mitigating risks through various strategies or interventions. However, it is essential to emphasize the importance of advocating for ethical and responsible utilization of AI in education in order to foster an environment of integrity and uphold academic honesty within schools.

Thus, the need for further research and responsible utilization of AI-powered tools is deemed necessary for a balanced approach that maximizes advantages while identifying solutions to minimize the risks involved.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Clear Ethical Guidelines and Supervision Mechanisms on the use of AI-powered tools should be established through the:
 - a. development of a comprehensive set of ethical guidelines specifically addressing concerns on academic integrity;
 - b. creation of a review process for evaluating AI tools considering factors such as their impact on student learning outcomes, potential biases, and alignment with educational objectives;
 - c. implementation of training sessions and seminars for educators, staff and students to ensure they understand and adhere to the ethical guidelines and are competent to supervise and monitor AI tool usage.
2. Critical Thinking Skills Development Activities should be integrated by means of:
 - a. designing interdisciplinary projects that require students to analyze and solve complex problems using AI-powered tools, encouraging them to critically evaluate information and consider multiple perspectives;
 - b. incorporating debate sessions or discussions focusing on the ethical implications of AI technologies, encouraging students to articulate their viewpoints and engage in respectful discourse.
3. Further research is encouraged and recommended to gain thorough understanding of the impact of artificial intelligence, maximize its potential benefits, and mitigate associated risks.

4. Proposed policy framework for the ethical use of AI should be utilized as bases for formulating comprehensive ethical guidelines anchored on the specific needs of the different educational institutions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In accordance with the ethical guidelines in conducting research, the researcher strictly followed the highest ethical standards in conducting the study. The manuscript underwent a thorough assessment by the Holy Name University Ethics Review Board to assure full compliance. Prior to conducting the study, the researcher fulfilled the necessary prerequisites, including obtaining a permission letter and endorsement from the Schools Division Superintendent, among other things.

Before the start of the interview, the participants were reminded of the importance of confidentiality and anonymity during the process, emphasizing that their responses would be treated with the utmost confidentiality and would not be attributed to them individually. The interview lasted for about 25-30 minutes. With the consent of the respondents, the said interview was recorded and later was transcribed. Participation in the study was purely voluntary and the participants were not bound to any responsibility. They might withdraw their participation anytime without penalty.

To ensure the participants' anonymity, strict measures were implemented throughout the research process. All collected data were stored securely and confidentially, with access limited to only to the researcher and authorized personnel directly involved in the study. During data analysis, any identifying information such as names or specific personal details were removed or replaced with codes to maintain confidentiality. After the conduct of the study, all data collected were destroyed. Additionally, in any future publications or presentations, participants would be referred to using generic terms or codes to further safeguard their anonymity.

POLICY FRAMEWORK ON THE ETHICAL UTILIZATION OF AI-POWERED TOOLS IN BASIC EDUCATION

I. RATIONALE

The rapid advancement and widespread adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) technology across various sectors of society have changed ways of life, occupations, and educational practices. Over the past few years, there has been a noticeable rise in the utilization of AI-powered tools within the field of education. These tools have demonstrated their ability to provide innovative methods aimed at improving the overall quality of teaching and learning experiences. The utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) tools in the field of education holds great promise, as it encompasses a wide range of applications which have the potential to bring about a transformative impact on education including customized assistance to students and simplifying administrative responsibilities for educators. However, the rapid adoption or use of these technologies

raises ethical concerns due to their adverse impacts like threats to academic integrity or dishonesty.

Considering the increasing prevalence and usage of AI-powered tools in learning institutions, it is necessary to establish a policy guideline that govern its utilization to ensure that all activities conducted in relation to AI is in line with the desired educational objectives and values. These guidelines can establish specific criteria that educators can follow when selecting and utilizing AI tools, with the aim of maximizing their advantages while reducing any associated risks.

The threat to academic integrity is considered one of the most significant potential risks associated with the utilization of AI-powered tools in education. Given the advanced capabilities of artificial intelligence (AI) in generating content and delivering prompt responses, it is important to acknowledge the potential increase in the risk of students resorting to AI tools that could lead to academic dishonesty, such as cheating or plagiarism. Policy guidelines play an important role in addressing the aforementioned risk by providing a framework that outlines clear standards and corresponding consequences for both students and educators with regards to the ethical utilization of AI technology in order to maintain academic integrity and prevent cheating.

Through the establishment and promotion of a culture centered around integrity and accountability, the implementation of policy guidelines can effectively safeguard the integrity of education. These guidelines serve the purpose of ensuring that AI-powered tools are utilized responsibly, with the primary objective of supporting student learning and fostering their overall development.

II. SCOPE

The scope of this policy is to establish a comprehensive framework for the ethical utilization of AI-Powered tools in the field of education, with the primary objective of upholding academic integrity.

This policy shall apply to:

1. School heads and administrators
2. Teaching and non-teaching personnel
3. Learners in public and private elementary and secondary schools

III. POLICY STATEMENT

This policy provides the framework and enabling mechanism for the ethical utilization of AI-powered tools in the basic education department. It is directed towards addressing the issues and concerns and the risks brought about by AI that challenge the integrity of educational process.

IV. POLICY GUIDELINES

A. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework outlined covers three major aspects: supervisory, instructional, and functional, each with its own goals and responsibilities aimed at ensuring the ethical utilization of AI-powered tools in education.

Under the supervisory aspect, school heads play an important role in understanding how AI may be appropriately used in education. This entails understanding the fundamental mechanisms of AI technologies, such as their potential, drawbacks, and possible impact on learning and teaching.

School principals are responsible to upholding academic integrity in the schools they supervise. With the emergence of AI technology, they must identify possible areas for academic misconduct caused by AI and adopt measures to prevent it. This may entail creating AI use policies, procedures, and ethical guidelines.

In the instructional aspect, teachers have the main task to revisit their instructional methodologies and assessment methods to effectively use AI in the teaching process. This could include revising pedagogies and developing ways to evaluate AI-generated work and give useful feedback to students. They are also entrusted with the responsibility of ensuring the proper use of AI tools, as well as providing guidance to students throughout the process.

For the functional aspect, teachers and ICT staff are responsible for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of AI in education. This includes monitoring student progress and determining the impact of AI on learning outcomes. Teachers and ICT staff must be equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to properly use and guide students with AI tools and technologies. This involves training in AI literacy, learning how

to use AI-powered instructional resources, and troubleshooting any technical challenges that may arise.

B. Guidelines and Procedures

1. The school governing body plays an important role in ensuring the effective and ethical utilization of AI technologies, making sure that they are in line with and promote the educational aims and objectives of the Department of Education.

2. The establishment of a culture of academic integrity within the school community, emphasizing the values of honesty, fairness, and ethical conduct in all academic endeavors must be given priority.

3. School heads should prioritize providing training and support for teachers and staff members to enhance their understanding of AI mechanisms and promote academic integrity in its utilization. This can be achieved through regular workshops and seminars focusing on understanding AI, ethical practices, and plagiarism detection.

4. The school administrators should lead by example, demonstrating ethical leadership in their own actions and decisions and promoting a culture of ethical behavior throughout the school community.

5. School heads should respond promptly and appropriately to any ethical concerns of academic misconduct in AI utilization, conducting thorough investigations and taking corrective actions as necessary to uphold academic integrity and maintain trust within the school community. They must ensure that claims of misconduct are investigated promptly, thoroughly, and impartially, with appropriate safeguards to protect the rights of all parties involved.

6. Teachers should serve as role models of ethical behavior in their own AI-related activities, demonstrating honesty, transparency, and integrity in their teaching, research, and interactions with students. If AI is used in preparing course materials, this should be acknowledged. Strategies for assessing AI-generated work should be developed in order to detect any forms of cheating.

7. ICT staff should support the implementation and enforcement of academic integrity policies and guidelines within the school. They should provide technical guidance and support to teachers and students through training and education sessions in using AI technologies and tools ethically and responsibly.

8. Students should be educated about copyright laws and intellectual property rights, emphasizing the importance of obtaining permission before using or sharing copyrighted materials and encourage originality and creativity while respecting the intellectual contributions of others.

9. A mechanism for monitoring compliance with academic integrity policies and guidelines, including the use of plagiarism detection tools, and investigation of reported violations should be implemented.

10. To uphold academic integrity in schools, it's essential to adhere to the following specific guidelines in using AI-powered tools:

a. The use of AI for completing assignments, tests, or any evaluations must be approved first by the teacher.

b. AI tools may be used as an aid in learning and research to gather information, identify relevant sources, and generate ideas for projects and essays, provided

that they are cited appropriately according to established citation styles (e.g., APA, MLA).

c. AI tools may be used to assist with grammar checks, sentence structure, and paraphrasing (with proper citation).

d. Assignments should emphasize critical thinking, problem-solving, and analysis to discourage relying solely on AI. When AI is used for this purpose, teachers have the right to request the original work logs from AI interactions if deemed necessary.

e. Teachers should ensure that AI projects and assignments are evaluated fairly and impartially, based on established criteria and standards. Evaluation criteria should be transparent, communicated in advance, and applied consistently to all students.

f. To check originality of assignments, teachers should employ strategies to detect AI-generated work. (e.g. asking students to discuss or present ideas in class, counter check submitted outputs.)

g. If a plagiarism checker is available, students will be asked to submit similarity index.

h. All forms of academic dishonesty are prohibited including:

- Copying, paraphrasing, or presenting AI-generated contents without proper acknowledgement
- Falsifying data or manipulating research results using AI tools
- Submitting AI-generated work as one's own without proper citation
- Using AI to conduct unauthorized collaboration on individual assignments
- Manipulating AI tools to excel in assessments and examinations
- Using AI to generate fake data or results
- Using of technology in the classroom to gain an unfair advantage over others
- Sharing exam questions or answers with AI-enabled cheating networks for unfair advantage

11. The consequences for violating the AI academic integrity policy should be clearly outlined and enforced to maintain the integrity of the academic institution.

The following are the suggested consequences:

a. Student Violations

First Offense:

- The student receives a formal warning and must attend a session on academic integrity or undergo counselling.
- The student may be required to redo the assignment.

Second Offense:

- The student may receive a failing grade for the subject in which the violation occurred.
- The student could be placed on academic probation for a specified period.

Repeated Offenses:

- The student may face suspension from the school.

- In severe or repeated cases, the student may be expelled from the institution.
- b. Faculty and Staff Violations:
- Faculty or staff may receive a formal reprimand and be required to undergo training.
 - Continued violations could lead to suspension or demotion.

V. Appeals Process

It is important that the consequences are proportionate to the severity of the violation and that they are consistently applied. The policy should also allow for discretion based on individual circumstances. An appeals process should be in place to ensure that disciplinary procedures are fair, consistent, and conducted in accordance with due process.

VI. Monitoring and Evaluation

The school administration shall oversee the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of this policy framework to ensure strict compliance. Appropriate monitoring, and evaluation tools shall be developed. This shall include the documentation of good practices as well as issues and challenges in the implementation of the Policy Framework and how they are addressed. Regular reviews will be conducted to assess the effectiveness of these guidelines and adapt them as necessary.

The adherence to this Academic Integrity Policy is essential for maintaining the credibility, reputation, and ethical standards of academic institutions in the age of AI. By steadfastly upholding these principles, it is hoped for that academic integrity will be preserved, fostering a culture characterized by honesty and excellence.

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